

Iqbal's Ideal Leader: and Beacon Of Light For Contemporary Leaders

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Journal of Quranic
and Social Studies
95-105

© The Author (s) 2023
Volume:3, Issue:2, 2023

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.

www.jqss.org

ISSN: E/ 2790-5640

ISSN: P/ 2790-5632

OJS **PKP**
OPEN JOURNAL SYSTEMS PUBLIC KNOWLEDGE PROJECT

Abstract

The concept of leadership exists in each and every nation .The leader is the mirror of the nation ,he can make or mar his nation through his good –will and ill-will .The Allama Iqbal concept of ideal leader “Mard-e-momin “is unique and carries the pivotal importance in the domain of Muslim philosophy .Allama Iqbal,s ideal leader is called as perfect man , Mard –e-Kamil is Holy Prophet (PBHP) .He embodies all best qualities . He is practical manifestation of ideal leader and perfect man .Allama Iqbal has developed deep love and reverence for Holy Prophet .The Holy Prophet life like a mirror . He is a perfect model for entire Muslim umma .If somebody going to analyze the life of Holy Prophet from any aspect ,he will found Him an ideal person in every walk of life . Holy Prophet was ideal as a teacher ,as a commander and as a trader . He is an ideal husband and father .He established the foundation of city-state of Madina ,which is the first welfare of entire world . The charter of Madina is the first written constitution of entire world ,which incorporates the essential elements of good governance . He is an exemplary rule and give patronage to all people of various communities . The qualitative and descriptive method will be adopted in this research work .The method of content-analysis will be adopted in data analysis part .The leadership theory will be applied on this research paper to assess the qualities of great and an ideal leader .What qualities are essential for an ideal leader ?The research work will be analyzed according to the ideal leadership model .The data collection will take place through various books , journals ,magazines , newspapers and internet websites etc.In the end ,the fact will be analysed and results will be extracted .The Allama Iqbal concept of Mard-e-momin carries pivotal importance that this leader is a beacon of light for the contemporary leaders . What message Allama Iqbal wants to convey to the modern Islamic leaders that how they can change their behavior by serving their nation and adopt the best qualities by following the model of Holy Prophet ?

Keywords: Mard-e-Momin, Holy Prophet, Ideal leader, Allama Iqbal, Nation

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